

65. Indian Adaptation of Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support in Hindi (MSPSS-Hindi)

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Social Support (SS) is shown to be correlated with measures of psychological well-being. It acts as a protective factor against stressors in life and thus be used as an indicator of wellbeing. Assessment of perceived social support can be an important step in formulating and administering family or community based interventions. Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) is a widely used scale for the assessment of social support covering three dimensions of perceived social support i.e. friends, family and significant other. Despite having been translated in several languages for different cultures, the Indian sample has been largely overlooked with no version of the MSPSS existing for the Hindi speaking population. The objective of the present study is hence to translate and adapt the MSPSS for use with Hindi speaking Indian population. To make the 12-items of MSPSS more culturally appropriate, they were translated to Hindi and then back translated to English and were subsequently subjected to systematic consultations before finalization. Psychometric properties of MSPSS-Hindi were calculated on a sample of 101 Hindi speaking participants (aged 18 to 50 years) from 13 states of India. Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.927$) was obtained to ensure internal consistency of the scale. Factorial validity of the scale was analyzed using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which indicated presence of two components that explained 73% of the variance. The first component corresponded to the family dimension, and the second component corresponded to both the friend and significant other dimension of perceived social support. Further scrutiny of significant other dimensions is required and other psychometric properties of MSPSS-Hindi are to be established.